

Toward a Breed-and-Burn Long-Life Core Design for Maritime Applications

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ABSTRACT

Over the last several years there has been an ever-increasing interest in using nuclear power in maritime applications, including Floating Nuclear Power Plants (FNPPs) and propulsion of commercial cargo ships. For economics considerations and non-proliferation concerns it is highly desirable to reduce the refueling frequency, i.e., to develop long-life core designs. This paper examines lead-cooled fast reactor (LFR) employing HALEU nitride fuel, aiming to exploit the breed-and-burn concept to extend the core lifetime and minimize the reactivity swing. Different unit cell geometries and enrichments were initially considered to identify the range of near-optimum solutions and inform the fuel assembly and full core analyses. Preliminary results indicate (at least in terms of reactivity) the feasibility of a 10–30-year core designs with discharge burnups of close to 150 GWd/tU with a low reactivity swing throughout the cycle. Future work will extend evaluation to confirm feasibility taking into account other design aspects and constraints.

Keywords: Maritime applications, nuclear-powered-propulsion, floating nuclear power plants, long-life core design, lead cooled fast reactor

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Motivation

Concerns related to environmental pollution and climate change require use of clean, low-emission energy sources including nuclear power and renewables. To make a global impact, power production cannot stay limited to electricity production but must additionally extend to non-electricity applications. In this context, there has been ever-increasing interest in maritime applications of nuclear power, for electricity production as well as for non-electricity applications, including Floating Nuclear Power Plants (FNPPs) and propulsion of large commercial cargo ships (e.g., container ships, tankers, bulk carriers, LNG, etc.).

The significant potential of these applications may be illustrated by the following. Maritime trade accounts for ~80% of global trade by volume and ~70% by value. Commercial cargo shipping, currently based on burning fossil fuel, consumes ~7% of primary fuel and generates ~3% of greenhouse gases. This is comparable to all of aviation (!) and replacing a notable portion of the propulsion power source would have a major impact. Moreover, FNPPs can be used to supply electricity as well as in co-generation or non-electricity application to provide process heat, desalination, and so on.

1.2. Historical Background and Feasibility

Both the nuclear propulsion and FNPP concept have historical and/or current actual implementations demonstrating their technical feasibility. Nuclear ship propulsion has been successfully used to power many naval vessel and a number of icebreakers; it has also been successfully demonstrated on 3 commercial cargo ships (NS Savannah [1], Otto Hahn [2] and Mutsu [3]) in 1960s and 1970s. A 10 MWe FNPP (MH-1A Sturgis, [4]) was operational in the Panama Canal Zone during 1967-1976 period. There is currently an operating FNPP, Akademik Lomonosov [5]. However, to enable their deployment at scale, there is a need to further develop and optimize, for

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each considered application, their technical aspects (reactor design, system design, etc.) as well as their economic viability.

1.3. Scope of this Work

To enable actual deployment, technical characteristics of these sources must meet the specific application's needs and be economically attractive. Economics is not addressed in this work; however, in an internal Georgia Tech study in 2009, economics was evaluated for a case where a large container ship fossil-fueled engine was replaced by SMR (integral PWR, IRIS [6]). The power level and everything else was kept the same, i.e., not optimized specifically for nuclear power. Economic analysis indicated potential for nuclear propulsion to be economical, i.e., cheaper than using fossil fuel. That work assumed a straightforward replacement of standard engine with a reactor of the same power. However, optimum engine power using fossil fuel is not necessarily the optimum power when using a nuclear reactor to provide power. A paper by Petrovic et al. [7] proposed novel approaches that may benefit from techno-economic characteristics of nuclear power to improve its economic attractiveness. It is based on the fact that while the capital cost is large for a nuclear reactor, nuclear fuel is relatively inexpensive. This allows using more energy at a limited cost, which in turn can increase the shipping throughput and thereby the profit of commercial nuclear propulsion. Further economic analysis [8] confirmed potential for economic competitiveness.

Beyond the technical aspect, for successful deployment it is (among others) necessary to achieve international public and governmental acceptance and implement effective international regulation and licensing. This is also not addressed in this paper, but it is currently under intense consideration by many interested entities; for representative reports, please see e.g. [9,10,11].

The focus and scope of this paper is limited to examining and developing core designs that enable long-life core and consequently reduce the refueling (or reactor replacement) frequency. For ship propulsion it would be beneficial to align refueling with major regular ship maintenance (every 5-10 years) or with ship lifetime (in most cases 25-30 years). For FNPPs, due to the need to tug them to a refueling facility, it is again desirable to reduce the refueling frequency and the associated idle time.

2. OBJECTIVES AND EVALUATION BASIS

2.1. Study Objectives

Two key core neutronics requirements critical for enabling the considered applications (commercial nuclear propulsion and FNPPs) were considered in this work:

- Long life core, defined as 7-10 years, with a stretch objective of extending it toward 25-30 years.
- Low reactivity swing to facilitate reactivity control.

Additionally, long life is to be achieved together with reactor operation at reasonably high specific power (measured by W/gHM), rather than simply by reducing the reactor power level. Consequently, the objective is to achieve relatively high discharge burnup (GWd/tHM) using fuel enriched to less than 20% if based on enriched uranium, or, with equivalent acceptable civilian enrichment if based on mixed fissile nuclides. High discharge burnup, in particular in straight burn mode, is facilitated through the breed-and-burn concept (B&B) where fissile material is first bred then consumed (burned) thereby extending the core lifetime while avoiding reprocessing. While other limitations may prevent achieving ideal near-complete B&B, we will use it as a notional goal. A system with a significant B&B contribution to the cycle length will also tend to have a reduced reactivity swing. B&B requires a fast system. In this paper we examine lead-cooled fast reactor (LFR) lattices employing HALEU nitride fuel. Future work is planned to extend this analysis to other reactor types and fuels including a Molten Chloride Salt Fast Reactor with TRU-based fuel. Heat removal and associated thermal performance limitations are only indirectly addressed through a selection of specific power consistent with published LFR designs and geometries within the envelope of the currently considered LFR designs. Similarly, materials considered in published literature have been used. Materials limitations have not been addressed yet; they will be addressed in follow-up work.

2.2. Baseline Unit Cell Model

Published LFR designs (such as ALFRED [12], SUNRISE [13] D-LFR [14], to give just a few representative designs) have been used to select a unit cell baseline. Variation of main parameters is then performed to achieve the target long life core.

A hexagonal unit cell is used in this study (Figure 1). Starting values of cell parameters are also given in Figure 1; they essentially follow ref. [13]. Uranium nitride (UN) fuel form is assumed as this is usually the fuel form of choice for LFRs. Nitrogen is assumed enriched to 99.5 wt% in ^{15}N . While in a fast spectrum the penalty due to ^{14}N is not as large as in a thermal spectrum system, it would make achieving long life core more challenging. Uranium enrichment is limited to commercially allowed HALEU (<20%). However, due to expected scarcity of enrichment close to 20%, it would be preferable to use LEU+ fuel (<10% enrichment). Even though this is anticipated not feasible, use of enrichment on the 10-15% range would be preferable since it can be obtained by mixing (assumed more available) LEU+ with limited amount of 19.75% enriched HALEU.

Figure 1. LFR unit cell geometry, materials and dimensions.

2.3. Code and Cross Sections Library Used

That core is depleted in the straight burn mode (single batch) corresponding to the full core (or full reactor replacement). Core depletion analysis was performed using the SCALE-6.3.1 code [15] with T6-DEPL sequence employing KENO-VI Monte Carlo code. Due to the very long execution time when using continuous energy (CE) cross sections, multigroup cross section library 'fine_fast_e8.0' was used instead for all reported results. This is a 302-group ENDF/B-VIII.0 based library [16] generated for sodium-cooled fast reactors (SFR). However, our previous studies have shown that it provides fairly accurate results (i.e., close to using continuous energy) for LFR as well [17], with multigroup multiplication factor k remaining within ~ 30 pcm from the reference continuous energy results over the full depletion range for the LFR design considered in that work. Limited spot checks comparing CE and MG results were still performed to confirm the validity of this approximation. Option ADDNEX=4 was used. This results in following the maximum number of nuclides in depletion analysis. Since in fast spectrum there are no large differences in cross sections, this seems prudent to avoid cumulated differences. Burnup steps were relatively long, after separate sensitivity analysis confirmed that it does not significantly impact accuracy of results. Simulation parameters were selected to obtain statistical convergence of the multiplication factor typically within 50 pcm (one sigma). This is deemed sufficient to analyze cycle length trends of interest for this study, but the statistical convergence may need to be tightened in future work.

3. PRELIMINARY SCOPING STUDIES USING PIN CELL MODEL

3.1. Analysis Methodology Using Pin Cell Results

Full 3D core simulations with depletion require significant computer resources and are not practical for initial scoping studies. On the other extreme, unit cell simulations are significantly faster but produce k -inf which (potentially significantly) overestimates the core multiplication factor k -eff since neutron leakage is not accounted for. However, they are more practical for initial scoping simulations since the computations are faster; additionally, and it avoids modifying the full complex core geometry model for each change. To evaluate whether pin cell results may be used – with appropriate corrections – to represent the reactivity of full core, several full core and analogous pin cell cases were simulated where the enrichment was changed from 10% to 11% to 12%. Figure 2 shows comparison of pin cell and full core multiplication factors over extended depletion as well as the difference in multiplication factor Δk (in pcm) in all 3 cases. The difference is fairly similar in all 3 cases, approximately in the range of 6% to 7.5%, k -eff of the full core being lower by that amount. Changing parameters other than enrichment may lead to some additional spread, but for moderate design changes we expect this adjustment to be valid for these initial scoping studies. We will use this difference to identify pin cell designs that are likely to result in acceptable (from the standpoint of reactivity) core design. To include some margin, we will require that the pin cell k -inf remains above 1.08 over the depletion range of interest.

Figure 2. Comparison of multiplication factors for pin cell (k -inf) and full core (k -eff), over the depletion up to 200 GWd/tU, for fuel enrichment of 10%, and 12% (top). Differences between k -inf and k -eff (bottom).

3.2. Reactivity Requirements

Reactivity requirements may be summarized as follows:

- Enrichment is below 19.75%, but preferably in the 10-15% range.
- K -inf of the pin-cell is above 1.08 over the burnup range of interest.

- Reactivity swing is low to facilitate reactivity control. From separate studies, it would be desirable to have reactivity swing below 5%.
- To achieve the desired core lifetime (10 years), reactivity-limited achievable discharge burnup should be at least 120 GWd/tU. (This estimate is based on separate analyses, assuming a specific power of the reactor and heavy metal loading of the core.)

3.3. Pin Cell Results

Pin cell depletion simulations were performed for 5 uranium enrichments ranging from 9% to 13%, with k -inf evolution over burnup shown in Figure 3. Based on the difference (due to leakage) between k -inf and k -eff in Figure 2, we may expect that the optimum enrichment for full core model will be in the range 10%-12%.

Figure 3. Comparison of multiplication factors for pin cell (k -inf) for fuel enrichment of 9%, to 13%.

4. LONG-LIFE CORE EVALUATION BASED ON 3D CORE DEPLETION

For the purpose of identifying fuel characteristics and enrichment that lead to B&B, we consider a LFR with nominal maximum power of 100 MW and corresponding specific power of 50 W/g having a 1 m active core height. A representative simplified 3D core model (not described in this paper) has been developed for studies described here. In future work, extending this study to detailed full core design, the specific power may be modified based on the desired thermal performance and safety envelope, but this is not expected to significantly impact the results in terms of achievable discharge burnup and low reactivity swing.

Figure 2 suggests that the 12% enrichment case, while providing somewhat higher discharge burnup, also starts with non-trivially higher multiplication factor, which may make the reactivity control significantly more complex. Also, the reactivity is decreasing over the cycle indicating that the benefit of breeding in this case is limited. On the other hand, the 10% enrichment case clearly demonstrates the breeding benefit, with the multiplication factor significantly increasing for the first 100 GWd/tU, but the reactor might not be critical at the beginning of cycle (BOC). Therefore, 11% enrichment has been additionally examined aiming to capture the benefits of both.

Figure 4 presents evolution of k -eff obtained by 3D full core depletion analysis, confirming predictions based on pin-cell simulations. Enrichments of 10% is subcritical while enrichment of 11% provides a critical core with some extra reactivity and fairly flat k -eff profile up to the ~ 150 GWd/tU, when the core becomes subcritical. A slightly higher enrichment may be desirable to provide a more comfortable operational margin. Enrichment of 12% would provide somewhat higher burnup (~ 165 GWd/tU), but at the expense of significantly higher initial excess reactivity that would need to be controlled.

Figure 4. Comparison of multiplication factors (k -eff) for 3D core (fuel enrichments 10%, 11% and 12%).

Further optimization will consider varying the lattice p/d parameters, implementing and evaluating reactivity control options, performing coupled neutronic-thermal-hydraulics analysis, as well as integrating it with an economic attractiveness analysis. Pin cell based scoping studies will again serve to initially explore a wider range of options and obtain trends that will then be verified in full 3D analyses.

Finally, we examine the evolution of fuel isotopic composition with burnup. Figures 5 and 6 present concentrations of uranium and main plutonium isotopes as a function of burnup. Initially, as U-235 is depleted, Pu-239 is generated at almost the same rate. After the Pu-239 concentration peaks (after 200 GWd/tU), both the U-235 and Pu-239 concentrations decline, and this would be reflected in declining reactivity as well. However, Pu-239 decline is relatively slow, and it is partly offset by Pu-241 generation.

Figure 5. Evolution of fuel isotopic composition (U and Pu) with depletion (logarithmic scale).

Figure 6. Evolution of fuel isotopic composition (U and Pu) with depletion (linear scale).

The plutonium isotopic vector shows high fraction of Pu-239 (i.e., high Pu “quality”), especially in the first half of the depletion, which may raise proliferation concerns. However, the long lifetime achieved by B&B allows lifetime operation without refueling, so that the reactor may be essentially “welded shut”, i.e., reactor fuel will not be accessible until the final removal at discharge burnup in a specialized facility.

Figure 7 depicts the concentration of fissile isotopes grouped as follows: U-235, Pu-239 plus Pu-241, and all three together. Note that the fission cross section is not the same for these isotopes and a more correct way of representing it would be to show the corresponding fission rates, but concentrations are more easily related to expected isotopic concentrations evolution. If weighted, the Pu line would be increased, and the total would be more flat, better explaining the relatively flat reactivity profile.

Figure 7. Evolution of fuel fissile isotops concentrations.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Use of nuclear power in maritime applications offers options to significantly contribute to reducing GHG emission, both by replacing fossil fuel for nuclear propulsion of commercial cargo ships, and by introducing Floating Nuclear Power Plants for electricity and non-electricity applications. In either case, long life reactor core is required to reduce refueling frequency. This work considered use of lead-cooled fast reactors (LFR) and examined core designs with hexagonal lattices employing HALEU nitride fuel, aiming to exploit the breed-and-burn concept to extend the core lifetime and minimize the reactivity swing. Pin cell simulations with appropriate correction factors were initially employed to enable evaluation of a larger number of cases. Three most promising cases were then analyzed with more accurate 3D models. Fuel with 11% enrichment provided the best reactivity characteristics, i.e., a fairly low reactivity swing (only 2% throughout the assumed cycle length) and the discharge burnup close to 150 GWd/tU. These results will guide future work that will include thermal-hydraulics as well as other requirements and limitations to holistically optimize and verify all aspects of the reactor design.

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